

Data Governance Plan for Madagascar Energy Access and Modelling

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Executive Summary

In Madagascar, the Ministry of Energy and Hydrocarbons, along with its entities including the Regulatory Office of Electricity and the Rural Electrification Development Agency, the national network manager is responsible for managing the country's energy sector. However, there is no structured approach to data management and governance, leading to fragmented practices. A data governance plan would ensure consistent, accurate, and up-to-date data for informed decisions and accurate modeling of energy needs and resources. This would promote data sharing among stakeholders, improve energy access, and enable evidence-based decision-making. A robust data governance plan would also help meet regulatory and compliance obligations, reducing legal and financial penalties.

1. Introduction

The main goal of the data governance plan is to create a structured framework that ensures geospatial and energy data in Madagascar is accurate, accessible, and secure. This framework will clearly define roles, responsibilities, and processes for managing data across all energy sector stakeholders. Additionally, the plan will encourage collaboration and data sharing among stakeholders to support coordinated energy access efforts. This plan covers all geospatial / non-geospatial and energy-related data relevant to electrification and clean cooking access in all areas of Madagascar involving the Ministry in charge of the energy sector, its entities, private operators, national network manager, technical and financial partners and donors, national statistics office, the other ministries.

2. Methodology

The first step to implementing a data governance plan is the data needs assessment based on geospatial (administrative boundaries, existing power plants, demographics...), and non-geospatial (energy consumption, regulations, and policy, ...)

Different data sources were identified including primary sources, secondary sources, and open data platforms

Primary data will be collected by using manual survey, GPS-enabled mobile devices, drones, sampling methods (collecting data from a subset of a larger population or set) and data acquisition from sensors and instruments, complemented by satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 for remote regions while, secondary data will be gathered as needed, based on the current project's requirements.

All energy access data must meet the accuracy and completeness standard of 90% as verified by the template established by the planning unit, within the Ministry in charge of Energy and against field survey ensuring that the datasets used in modeling are reliable and actionable.

Furthermore, another necessary step includes data cleaning and formatting and a combination of different datasets (data harmonization, data fusion, interoperability) Datasets must be at least two years current. In case of data gaps (virtually non-existent sources, etc.), data should be subject to prior review by the Ministry of Energy before use. The data governance plan will comply with the Electricity law n° 2017-020 and align with the law n°2014-006 on fighting cybercrime, law n° 2014 - 038 for managing personal data, and any regulations specific for the energy sector and international standards ensuring that all data processes are legally compliant.

3. Results

This table gives the different data sources identified for Madagascar:

Type	Data source
Primary data	Field surveys conducted by the Ministry in Charge of Energy, Regulatory Office, Rural electrification agency, Private operator PCD (Community development plan)
Secondary Data	INSTAT (National Institute of Statistics): https://dataviz.instat.mg/accueil FTM (Madagascar's national mapping agency): link not available Other ministries (Health, education, economy and finance, water, agriculture, environment, interior and decentralization, ...)
Open Data Platforms	IEP (Integrated Energy Access Platform): https://madagascar.sdg7energyplanning.org/dashboard/mdg-iep OpenStreetMap: https://www.openstreetmap.org/ GEP (Global Electrification Plateform): https://electrifynow.energydata.info ENERGYDATA.INFO: https://energydata.info/dataset?vocab_country_names=MDG Humanitarian data exchange : https://data.humdata.org/

The table below shows the main datasets collected in this case study:

Dataset	Source type	Source	Format	Year of update	Accuracy
Administrative boundaries	Secondary	INSTAT	Vector	2018	yes
Power plants	Secondary	JIRAMA	Vector	2021	yes
Mini grid Power plant	Secondary	ADER	Vector	2023	yes
MV/HV Transmission network	Secondary	JIRAMA	Vector	2021	yes
Substation	Secondary	JIRAMA	Vector		yes
Hydroelectric potential	Secondary	MEH	Vector		yes
Solar potential	Secondary	MEH	Vector		yes
Population	Secondary	INSTAT	Vector	2018	yes

The database will follow a relational model outlined in the proposed database schema linked through unique identifiers for each geographical region.

This diagram shows for each municipality the electricity consumption per year, per customer category, and also the power plant center by energy source and energy producer.

The structure of the schema , including tables relationships and key attributes, is:

- **Commune** : Location of municipalities by region, district
- **ExistingPowerPlant** : Power plant by type of source, energy producer, and year of commissioning
- **Consumption** : Energy consumption per year and per customer category
- **MV Line** : Medium voltage transmission line with length and voltage level
- **ClientCategory** : Customer category
- **SourceEnergy** : Energy source
- **Energy producer** : List of electricity operators

From this database, the analyses below can be outstanding:

- Energy Production by source per municipality per year with MV line
- The largest electricity operator by the number of production points
- Municipality electrified and not electrified: not Electrified means consumption is 0

4. Discussion

By implementing the data Governance Structure established in this study, it will:

- Promote fluent collaboration between stakeholders in the Energy sector
- Maintain high data quality standards,
- Support informed decision-making and advance energy access efforts,
- Enhance energy planning results ensuring that the datasets used in modelling are reliable and actionable,

This cohesive approach will contribute to a more sustainable and efficient energy system in the country. Additionally, proper data processing and integration are vital to ensure that the data used in modeling is accurate, dependable, and actionable for real-world applications

To ensure compliance with regulations, and relevant standards and foster trust among stakeholders, measures are proposed to safeguard the integrity, confidentiality, and availability of project data. The security plan will include access control, data encryption, security audits, and compliance review.

Additionally, conducting regular reviews and updates to this plan to adapt to evolving security threats and shifting project requirements is recommended. This proactive approach will help the system stay ahead of potential risks and maintain the highest levels of data protection throughout the project's lifecycle.

To align with the law requirements, it is recommended that the Ministry of Energy develop a Strategic Plan for data management that sets clear objectives, defines responsibilities, and establishes a timeline for updates and evaluations. Establishing a dedicated data governance working group to oversee and guide data maintenance, upgrades, and stakeholder engagement is also crucial. Furthermore, identifying and addressing the training needs of staff should be prioritized to ensure that all parties involved acquire the necessary skills for effective data management.

To support the sustainability of the data governance framework, a dedicated team comprising data managers, data owners, and IT specialists from each entity within the ministry should be maintained. Securing funding for both human and technical resources through the Ministry's annual budget, supplemented by financial and technical partners, is essential. Furthermore, regular servers, software licenses, and cloud storage assessments and upgrades should be carried out to ensure the infrastructure remains robust and capable of meeting evolving data management needs.

Limitations of study:

A risk assessment identified the potential for data breaches as a significant threat, particularly during data transmission over public networks

Risks of non-compliance with data protection regulations or contractual obligations: existing policies and regulations do not support explicitly the rapid adoption of the new framework, leading to delays or partial implementation

Cultural and Institutional Resistance: Some entities may resist the new data governance framework due to entrenched practices

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the data governance plan is a crucial step toward enhancing energy access and modeling in Madagascar. By establishing clear standards for data quality, documentation, and management, this plan will empower stakeholders with reliable, accurate, and timely information, leading to more informed decision-making and better outcomes for our energy initiatives. The implementation of this plan will not only improve data management but also foster stronger collaboration among stakeholders, ensuring that all efforts are aligned and focused on achieving our shared goals, especially for global access to electricity and clean cooking.

The timeline will be implemented as soon as all the stakeholders and the working group toward full deployment of the framework are gathered. As we move forward, every stakeholder must remain committed to the plan. Together, we can create a robust data governance framework that will drive sustainable energy solutions and contribute to the development of Madagascar.

Now is the time to take action. Let's work together to turn this plan into reality and unlock the full potential of our data to make a lasting impact on the future of energy in Madagascar

Appendices

Appendix B: Data Governance Structure Diagram

Appendix C:

- Law 2017-020 on the Electricity Code in Madagascar,
- Décret n°2023-245 du 11 mars 2023 fixant les procédures relatives aux Concessions de Production, de Transport et de Distribution ; aux Autorisations de Production et de Distribution et aux Déclarations de Production d'énergie électrique
- Arrêté n° 20027/2022/MEH portant mise en vigueur des Codes de Réseaux de Transport

et de Distribution d'Énergie Électrique à Madagascar

- Law 2014 - 038 on the protection of personal data
- Law 2014-006 on the fight against Cybercrime in Madagascar